

How do I learn?

Survey on self-regulated learning strategies for apprentices

With this survey, we want to find out more about how you learn.

- Please read every answer carefully and click on the option that fits you best.
- There are no right or wrong answers. This is about how you as an individual learn and think.

Answer options:

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often
- Always

Planning (metacognitive strategy)

1. Before I start to study, I think about the order in which I want to work through the material.
2. Before I start to study, I think about how I want to proceed.
3. Before I start to study, I think about which parts I must learn and which are not so important for me.

Monitoring (metacognitive strategy)

4. I repeat the most important points without checking my notes or a book, to find out whether I understood everything.
5. I ask myself questions about the things I learned to test if I understood the subject matter.
6. I do additional, voluntary exercises to test if I really understand the subject matter.

Reflecting

7. When I'm done with an exercise or a workpiece, I stop to think whether my results are good.
8. When I'm done with an exercise or a workpiece, I stop to think what I could do better the next time.
9. When I get feedback or an assessment of my work, I read it carefully.
10. When I get feedback or an assessment of my work, I think about how I could improve my work.
11. When I think carefully about what I've learned after lessons, it's easier for me to prepare for tests.

Adaptation (metacognitive strategy)

12. I adapt my method when there's a difficult problem at hand, for example, I break it up into smaller tasks.
13. When I'm not clear about something during studying, I revise it again slowly.
14. When I'm reading a text and there are parts that I don't understand, I keep them in mind and read it through again.

Elaboration (cognitive strategy)

15. When I study, I think about how the different things are connected.
16. During studying, I rephrase important things in my own words.
17. When I have to remember new concepts, I come up with examples.

18. I connect the things I learn with the things I already know.
19. I think about how the things I learn relate to my everyday life.

Organisation (cognitive strategy)

20. I underline or highlight important words and sentences in my learning materials (books, worksheets, notes).
21. I sort my learning materials in a way that I can remember everything easily.
22. I write short summaries with the most important points from my learning materials (books, worksheets, notes).

Revising (cognitive strategy)

23. I put the most important technical terms in a list and revise them.
24. When reading a text, I try to revise important points at the end of each paragraph.
25. I learn rules, formulas, and technical terms by heart.

Recognising the essential (cognitive strategy)

26. It's easy for me to decide what I should remember from the script.
27. During lessons, I can tell important and less important things apart.
28. While reading, I can easily spot the important points.

Making an effort (support strategy)

29. When I've set the goal to study a certain amount of content, I make an effort to achieve it.
30. I don't give up, even when the subject matter is difficult.
31. I allocate enough time to revise the whole subject matter before an exam.
32. I make an effort, even when the subject matter is not interesting for me at all.

33. Please finish this sentence:

"For me, reflection means..."

Thank you very much! 😊